

THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON SOCIAL PROBLEMS AMONG MIGRANT WORKERS IN CHENNAI DISTRICT, TAMILNADU

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Abstract

India, migrant workers confront a variety of difficulties and threats, including exploitation, harassment, assault, trafficking, bonded labour, low pay, unsafe working conditions, and lack of social protection, health concerns, and exclusion from development initiatives. To analyse basic social aspects and the impact of COVID-19 on migrant workers. To find the association between social problems and COVID-19. In the field of migration studies, there has been very less number of research on the relationship between pandemics and migration before COVID-19. In general, there has been growing attention in the field to the key topic of health-related migration. When people living in this motherland work in different parts of the country to support their families financially through construction workers, hotel workers, miners, cleaners, agricultural workers, restaurant workers, retail, transport workers, social workers, maid and so on they face lot of problems out of them one is social aspects. This research made an attempt to bring the problems faced by the migrant workers during the pandemic situation. The p-value (Sig.) associated with the F-statistic is 0.029, 0.011, 0.007, 0.316, 0.003, and 0.000 of gender, age, marital status, religion, education and duration of stay in Chennai respectively. Since the p-value is lesser than the typical significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected and H₁ is accepted based on the results of the ANOVA. The statistical analysis is concluded that there is a constant relationship between the social aspects among the emigrant workers.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

India, migrant workers confront a variety of difficulties and threats, including exploitation, harassment, assault, trafficking, bonded labour, low pay, unsafe working conditions, and lack of social protection, health concerns, and exclusion from development initiatives. Additionally, they have trouble getting essential services like banking, legal assistance, identity documentation, education, and health care. There has been a steady increase in the country in the number of migrants. Where as in 1961 there were about 144 million migrants by place of birth, in 2001 Census, it was 307 million) people in India were migrants. This was about 27 per cent of the Indian population, the survey estimate of the total population in India being about 921 million.

Although relatively marginal in the field of migration studies, there has been research on the relation between pandemics and migration before COVID-19. In general, there has been growing attention in the field to the key topic of health-related migration, but also the health situation of migrants and their access to healthcare.

Since 2020, there have been numerous publications on COVID-19 and migration. Some focus on how the pandemic is challenging and reshaping migration patterns. The pandemic has

revealed dilemmas of dependency of various countries that increasingly rely on labour migrants for their economic production but are no longer able to recruit and receive labour migrants during the pandemic.

India is a riverine and agricultural based country. Agriculture is the main source of livelihood for the people of India and the country's economic base is being built with this agricultural power. People living in this motherland work in different parts of the country to support their families financially through construction workers, hotel workers, miners, cleaners, agricultural workers, restaurant workers, retail, transport workers, social workers, maid and so on.

The government of India launched a nationwide lockdown in March 2020 to protect the country from the deadly harmful virus covid-19. Migrant workers face various problems. Millions of migrant workers lose their jobs as a result of coronavirus lockdown in India. As a result, they have to walk about 400 to 1000 km by road to get back home. Burning examples are still floating in the eyes of India and the world through newspapers, TV and radio.

The COVID-19 pandemic will likely impact the world's poorest and most vulnerable countries and people the hardest. Undoubtedly, migrants and refugees in vulnerable situations, their families, and communities reliant on the development outcomes of migration, will suffer. Those with informal or unstable employment, entrepreneurs and those working in the service industry (a majority of whom are women) are most affected, with only 1 in 5 unemployed persons able to access unemployment benefits.

Ensuring the portability of social benefits will limit migrants' and refugees' exposure to the risks of being exploited and falling below the poverty line. There is also an important gender dimension, as women disproportionately work in insecure, more precarious, lower-paid, part-time and informal employment, and as unpaid workers in farms and family businesses.

These workers can be subject to harassment or violence and often have little or no income security and social protection, which means that they are less protected from economic recession in times of crisis. The return of migrants to countries of origin and the reduction of remittances sent home will likely surpass the capacity of the formal and informal sectors in those countries to absorb large numbers of returnees or additional local job seekers in the local labour market due to reduced remittances. Closure of borders, restrictions to free movement and barriers to trade will also render cross-border traders and value chains in key products more vulnerable

The COVID-19 pandemic led to an unprecedented level of social expressions of solidarity and support across different groups within society, regardless of socio-economic status and background. At the same time, it has laid bare structural inequalities and vulnerabilities within society, as well as episodes of discrimination towards migrants. In many countries, ethnic minorities have been is proportionally affected by the virus and have experienced higher mortality rates. As the crisis continues, it is likely that there will be increased tension and conflict within society, threatening to reinforce social exclusion of disadvantaged groups, including migrants and refugees in vulnerable situations. There have already been documented

cases of stigma, discrimination and xenophobic attacks globally. Not only can this further hamper social cohesion in the long term, but it also has immediate consequences as it jeopardizes the safety of migrants, refugees, and their communities, as well as their physical and mental well-being, as well as the overall safety of the host country and community. Development partners must focus on taking a whole-of-community approach and addressing tension and distrust in the socio-economic response.

1.2 REVIEWS

Cuiyan Wang et al. and Riyu Pan (2019) predicted that the 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19) epidemic in China is a global health threat, and is by far the largest outbreak of atypical pneumonia since the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) outbreak in 2003. Within weeks of the initial outbreak the total number of cases and deaths exceeded those of SARS. The outbreak was first revealed in late December 2019 when clusters of pneumonia cases of unknown aetiology were found to be associated with epidemiologically linked exposure to a seafood market and untraced exposures in the city of Wuhan of Hubei Province. Since then, the number of cases has continued to escalate exponentially within and beyond Wuhan, spreading to all 34 regions of China by 30 January 2020. On the same day, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the COVID-19 outbreak a public health emergency of international concern., Anand, et al., (2020) Bernes, T., Brozus et al., (2020) De, Prabir (2021).

1.3 OBJECTIVES

1. To analyse basic social aspects and the impact of COvid 19 of migrant workers
2. To find the association between social problems and Covid-19

1.4 AREA PROFILE AND SAMPLE SIZE

The Chennai district formerly known as Madras district is the smallest of all districts in the State, but has the highest human density. Chennai district covers an area of 178.2 km located on the Eastern Coastal Plains of India. It lies between 12°59' and 13°9' of the Northern latitude and 80°12' and 80°19' of the Eastern longitude at an average altitude of 6 meters above sea level on a 'sandy shelving breaker swept' beach.

According to Chennai District Human Development Report (2017) Chennai is one of the 32 districts in Tamil Nadu which is fully urban (100%) in character. Chennai is well connected by all means of transportation Chennai otherwise called as Madras city is the Capital city for the State of Tamil Nadu. Chennai is the fourth largest metropolitan city in India with an area of 174sq.km and a population of 4.68 million (as per census 2011).

The city of Chennai is classified into three regions: North Chennai, Central Chennai and South Chennai. It is further divided into 15 zones, consisting of 200 wards. The primary data has been collected from the above mentioned area six zones were selected from the fifteen zones. Moreover, in the firts stage zones were identified as Madhavaarm from North border of Chennai (zone III), Rayapuram from East Border of Chennai (Zone V), Ambattur from North

West Border of Chennai (Zone VII) , Annanager from Middle of Chennai (Zone VII), Aalandur from South west of Chennai (Zone XII). And Perungudi from South border of Chennai (Zone XIV).

In second stage 2 clusters from each zones where there are number of working spot and migrants were found which was obtained from key informants (contractors) later, from each clusters 30-35 samples were collected randomly and therefore totally 411 samples. The researcher has made confidence with the migrant workers and the contractors this data collection purely for the research purpose and certainly the results will help for the betterment of the migrant workers in future. With this statement, it was sable to collect the data from the migrant's workers in Chennai. After collection of data entered in to XECL spread sheet, later to SPSS. To analyse the data and conclude the results the appropriate statistical tool has been applied.

1.5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table-1: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Gender and Livelihood

Gender/ Livelihood	Male	Female	Total
BEFORE COVID			
Unemployed	34 (77.3)	10 (23.7)	44
Partially	12 (85.7)	2 (14.3)	14
Employed	283 (80.2)	70 (19.8)	353
DURING COVID			
Unemployed	227 (80.2)	56 (19.6)	283
Partially	90 (80.4)	22 (19.6)	112
Employed	12 (75.0)	4 (25.0)	16
AFTER COVID			
Unemployed	85 (82.5)	18 (17.5)	103
Partially	29 (82.9)	6 (17.1)	35
Employed	215 (78.8)	58 (21.2)	273

(Figures Percentages are in the parenthesis)

Fig 1

The above Fig-1 infers that Gender and livelihood of the respondents in three different situations such as before covid, during and after the covid-19. Of the total, 86 percent were employed; the remaining were partially employed or unemployed. Among male were 80 percent and female was 20 percent. During the covid around 8 -10 percent of the male and female were unemployed but after eh covid again they had lost their job opportunities and hence partially employed and unemployed proportion have increased. The data analysis showed that the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on livelihoods with males generally having a higher presence in full-time employment. Of the total of 411 individuals studied, a majority are being employed (353 individuals) before Corona. Males dominated the employed category, comprising 80.2%, while females made up 19.8% of the employed individuals. In contrast, a smaller number of individuals were unemployed (44), with 77.3% males and 23.7% females. Partial employment was relatively rare, with 14 individuals, primarily male (85.7%). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the employment landscape shifted significantly. A larger proportion of individuals found themselves unemployed (283 in total), with 80.2% being male and 19.6% female. Similarly, partial employment increased to 112 individuals, again predominantly male (80.4%). The number of individuals in full-time employment dropped substantially to just 16, with 75.0% male and 25.0% female during the pandemic. After the pandemic, the data shows a partial recovery in employment. The number of unemployed individuals decreased to 103, with 82.5% male and 17.5% female. Partial employment also decreased to 35 individuals, with 82.9% male and 17.1% female.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Religion and Livelihood

Livelihood and Religion	Hindus	Muslims	Christians	Doesn't disclose	Total
Before Covid					
Unemployed	30 (68.2)	6 (13.6)	8 (18.2)	0 (.0)	44
Partially / Occasionally employed	9 (64.3)	1 (7.1)	4 (28.6)	0 (.0)	14
Employed	295 (83.6)	10 (2.8)	42 (11.9)	6 (1.7)	353
During Covid					
Unemployed	229 (80.9)	12 (4.2)	36 (12.7)	6 (2.1)	283
Partially / Occasionally employed	98 (87.5)	4 (3.6)	10 (8.9)	0 (.0)	112
Employed	7 (43.8)	1 (6.2)	8 (50.0)	0 (.0)	16
After Covid					
Unemployed	92 (89.3)	2 (1.9)	9 (8.7)	0 (.0)	103
Partially / Occasionally employed	33 (94.3)	1 (2.9)	1 (2.9)	0 (.0)	35
Employed	209 (76.6)	14 (5.1)	44 (16.1)	6 (2.2)	273

(Figures Percentages are in the parenthesis)

Table-2 illustrates the percentage of employment and their religion. The table suggests that before COVID, majority of Hindu respondents were employed (83.6%), with a smaller percentage being unemployed. Muslim respondents had a higher percentage of unemployment (13.6%) compared to other religious groups. During the lockdown, the percentage of Hindu respondents who were unemployed increased significantly (80.9%). Muslim respondents recorded a higher unemployment rate (4.2%) while Christian respondents also saw an increase in unemployment (12.7%). In comparing the before COVID and after the lifting of the lockdown Muslims and Christians have steady employment rates. After the COVID lockdown the partial employment has increased among the Hindus from 64% to 94% which is notable. However, it is important to note that unemployment among Hindu respondents dropped from 84% to 77%.

Table 3: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Social Group and Livelihood

Livelihood Status and Social Group	SC	ST	BC	FC	No Caste	Not Aware	Total
BEFORE COVID							
Unemployed	15 (34.1)	5 (11.4)	5 (11.4)	2 (4.5)	15 (34.1)	2 (4.5)	44
Partially / Occasionally employed	9 (64.3)	0 (.0)	2 (14.3)	0 (.0)	2 (14.3)	1(7.1)	14
Employed	185 (52.4)	9(2.5)	101 (28.6)	4(1.1)	44 (12.5)	10 (2.8)	353
DURING CORONA							
Unemployed	120 (42.4)	13 (4.6)	86 (30.4)	2 (.7)	53 (18.7)	9 (3.2)	283
Partially / Occasionally employed	85 (75.9)	0 (.0)	20 (17.9)	1 (.9)	5 (4.5)	1 (.9)	112
Employed	4 (25.0)	1(6.2)	2 (12.5)	3 (18.8)	3 (18.8)	3 (18.8)	16
AFTER CORONA							
Unemployed	86 (83.5)	0 (.0)	16 (15.5)	0 (.0)	1 (1.0)	0 (.0)	103
Partially / Occasionally employed	9 (25.7)	1 (2.9)	23 (65.7)	0 (.0)	2 (5.7)	0 (.0)	35
Employed	114 (41.8)	13 (4.8)	69 (25.3)	6 (2.2)	58 (21.2)	13 (4.8)	273

(Figures Percentages are in the parenthesis)

From the above table-3, it is observed that the SC and No Caste groups had the highest unemployment percentages (34.1% each). The BC and FC groups had relatively lower unemployment percentages. The BC group had the highest percentage of employed individuals (28.6%). However, during COVID the SC, ST, and “No Caste” groups had high unemployment percentages. The FC group had the highest percentage of employed individuals (18.8%). After COVID migrants from SC & ST caste had the highest unemployment percentage (83.5%) while the BC and FC groups had lower unemployment percentages. It is observed that SC & ST group consistently had high unemployment percentages before, during, and after COVID. The BC and FC groups generally had higher percentages of employed individuals. This proves that the higher caste group migrants are not affected much by the impact of the COVID in their employment status.

Table 4: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Level of Education and Livelihood

Livelihood /Education	Illiter	Prima	Secon	HSec	Tech	Gradu	Total
BEFORE COVID							
Unemployed	0 (.0)	13 (29.5)	14 (31.8)	7 (15.9)	2 (4.5)	8 (18.2)	44
Partially / Occasionally employed	0 (.0)	2 (14.3)	4 (28.6)	2 (14.3)	0 (.0)	6 (42.9)	14
Employed	33 (9.3)	108 (30.6)	104 (29.5)	68 (19.3)	4 (1.1)	36 (10.2)	353
DURING COVID							
Unemployed	26 (9.2)	68 (24.0)	93 (32.9)	59 (20.8)	4 (1.4)	33 (11.7)	283
Partially / Occasionally employed	7 (6.2)	54 (48.2)	26 (23.2)	17 (15.2)	0 (.0)	8 (7.1)	112
Employed	0 (.0)	1 (6.2)	3 (18.8)	1 (6.2)	2 (12.5)	9 (56.2)	16
AFTER COVID							
Unemployed	5 (4.9)	50 (48.5)	28 (27.2)	17 (16.5)	0 (.0)	3 (2.9)	103
Partially / Occasionally employed	1 (2.9)	7 (20.0)	14 (40.0)	8 (22.9)	3 (8.6)	2 (5.7)	35
Employed	27 (9.9)	66 (24.2)	80 (29.3)	52 (19.0)	3 (1.1)	45 (16.5)	273

(Figures Percentages are in the parenthesis)

Illiter- Illiterate, Prima-Primary, Scon-Secondary, HSec- Higher Secondary, Tech- Technical graduate, Gradua- Graduate Table 4 presents the percentage distribution of respondents by Level of education of the migrant workers and livelihood in COVID-19 pandemic. The majority of unemployed migrant individuals had primary education (29.5%) or were illiterate (31.8%). Those who have completed secondary education (29.5%) or primary education (30.6%), higher secondary education (19.3%) and graduates (10.2%) had good employment opportunities. However during COVID lockdown the unemployment is faced by all categories to an extent with secondary education (32.9%) being the highest. The number of employed for graduates had dropped from 36 to 9 which is 75%. After the lifting of lockdown, the unemployment percentages were relatively evenly distributed across literacy levels, with primary education (48.5%) being the highest. The graduates had more opportunities after the COVID as their employment rates increased by 25%. In conclusion the COVID had affected the illiterate and limited levels of education in their employment. However during COVID, those who are in lower levels of education had been engaged in employment partially & occasionally. Unmarried individuals faced higher unemployment rates during the pandemic compared.

Table 5: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status and Livelihood

Marital status and Livelihood	Married	Un Married	Divorced	Separated	Not willing to share	Total
BEFORE COVID						
Unemployed	30 (68.2)	13 (29.5)	0 (.0)	1 (2.3)	0(.0)	44
Partially / Occasionally employed	6 (42.9)	7 (50.0)	0 (.0)	1(7.1)	0(.0)	14
Employed	307 (87.0)	25 (7.1)	8 (2.3)	12 (3.4)	1(.3)	353
DURING COVID						
Unemployed	230 (81.3)	33 (11.7)	8 (2.8)	11 (3.9)	1(.4)	283
Partially / Occasionally employed	101 (90.2)	8 (7.1)	0 (.0)	3 (2.7)	0 (.0)	112
Employed	12 (75.0)	4(25.0)	0 (.0)	0 (.0)	0 (.0)	16
AFTER COVID						
Unemployed	99 (96.1)	4 (3.9)	0 (.0)	0 (.0)	0 (.0)	103
Partially / Occasionally employed	32 (91.4)	2 (5.7)	0 (.0)	0 (.0)	1 (2.9)	35
Employed	212 (77.7)	39 (14.3)	8 (2.9)	14 (5.1)	0 (.0)	273

(Figures Percentages are in the parenthesis)

The above Fig-2 infers that Livelihood Status and Marital Status of the respondents in three different situations such as before Covid, during and after the Covid-19. Out of the 411 samples 83.5% of them were married followed by 10.9% of them unmarried. The divorced, separated and not willing to share constituted to rest of 6%. Before Covid 87% of the married people and 7% of the unmarried were employed. However the employment structure changed significantly during the Covid 19 lockdown. A significant proportion of married individuals were employed (87.0%), with a smaller percentage being unemployed (68.2%) or partially employed (42.9%). This suggests that most married individuals were actively working. During Covid a similar trend continued for married individuals, however Unmarried individuals, on the other hand, saw a significant increase in unemployment (11.7%) during COVID, with a decrease in partial employment (7.1%). After the pandemic, the employment rate for married individuals remained relatively stable (77.7%), with a very low unemployment rate (3.9%). Unmarried individuals showed a similar trend as before COVID, with some unemployment (3.9%) and partial employment (5.7%). The data suggests that divorced and separated individuals did not experience significant changes in employment status during or after the pandemic. Married individuals consistently had the highest employment rates and the lowest unemployment rates throughout the three periods.

Fig-2

Table 6: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Livelihood Status and Years of Stay in Chennai

Livelihood Status / No of years in Chennai	5 Years (+)	4 Years	3 Years	2 Years	< 1Year	Total
BEFORE COVID						
Unemployed	18 (40.9)	6 (13.6)	8 (18.2)	10 (22.7)	2 (4.5)	44
Partially / Occasionally employed	8 (57.1)	1 (7.1)	0 (.0)	2 (14.3)	3 (21.4)	14
Employed	207 (58.6)	98 (27.8)	14 (4.0)	7 (2.0)	27 (7.6)	353
DURING COVID						
Unemployed	171 (60.4)	59 (20.8)	12 (4.2)	15 (5.3)	26 (9.2)	283
Partially / Occasionally employed	53 (47.3)	42 (37.5)	8 (7.1)	3 (2.7)	6 (5.4)	112
Employed	9 (56.2)	4 (25.0)	2 (12.5)	1 (6.2)	0 (.0)	16
AFTER COVID						
Unemployed	49 (47.6)	42 (40.8)	7 (6.8)	1 (1.0)	4 (3.9)	103
Partially / Occasionally employed	30 (85.7)	2 (5.7)	0 (.0)	3 (8.6)	0 (.0)	35
Employed	154 (56.4)	61 (22.3)	15 (5.5)	15 (5.5)	28 (10.3)	273

(Figures Percentages are in the parenthesis)

Table-6 illustrates the percentage distribution of respondents by livelihood status and the number of years they have stayed in Chennai before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Unemployed individuals had varying years of stay in Chennai, with the highest percentage (40.9%) having stayed for 5 years or more. A significant portion (22.7%) had stayed for 2 years. During the COVID lockdown those who have stayed in Chennai for more than 4 years have got employment. The employed group had a majority (56.2%) who had stayed in Chennai for 5 years or more than the new migrants with less years in Chennai. However after the lifting of the COVID lockdown the new migrants to Chennai have higher levels of employment compared to those who have settled in Chennai for more than 5 years. Those who were living in Chennai for the last 5 years have dropped by 24%.

Table 7: Association Between Impact of Covid -19 And Social Problems Among Migrant Workers in Chennai District

H0: There is no association between impact of covid -19 and social problems among migrant workers

H1: There is association between impact of covid -19 and social problems among migrant workers

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	.275	1	.275	1.118	.029
	Within Groups	100.635	409	.246		
	Total	100.910	410			
Age	Between Groups	118.828	1	118.828	2.537	.011
	Within Groups	19156.690	409	46.838		
	Total	19275.518	410			
Marital Status	Between Groups	.569	1	.569	1.024	.007
	Within Groups	9707.669	409	23.735		
	Total	9708.238	410			
Religion	Between Groups	.804	1	.804	1.009	.316
	Within Groups	325.955	409	.797		
	Total	326.759	410			
Education	Between Groups	.019	1	.019	.010	.003
	Within Groups	777.461	409	1.901		
	Total	777.479	410			
Duration of staying in Chennai	Between Groups	1.900	1	1.900	1.289	.000
	Within Groups	602.674	409	1.474		
	Total	604.574	410			

The ANOVA tests whether there is a statistically significant difference in the dependency association between impact of covid -19 and social problems among migrant workers in Chennai district. The F-statistic is 1.118, 2.537, 1.024, 1.009, 0.10, 1.289 which is a measure of the variation between the groups relative to the variation within the groups of gender, age, marital status, religion, education, and duration of stay in Chennai. This value indicates that there is some difference in dependency on social problems with the covid-19. The p-value (Sig.) associated with the F-statistic is 0.029, 0.011, 0.007, 0.316, 0.003, and 0.000 of gender, age,

marital status religion education and duration of stay in Chennai respectively. Since the p-value is lesser than the typical significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected and H₁ is accepted based on the results of the ANOVA:

1.6 FINDINGS

Gender and livelihood of the respondents in three different situations such as before covid, during and after the covid-19. Of the total, 86 percent were employed; the remaining were partially employed or unemployed. Among male were 80 percent and female was 20 percent. During the covid around 8 -10 percent of the male and female were unemployed but after covid again they had lost their job opportunities and hence partially employed and unemployed proportion have increased. The data analysis showed that the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on livelihoods with males generally having a higher presence in full-time. The statistical test for the data through the ANOVA tests whether there is a statistically significant difference in the dependency association between impact of covid -19 and social problems among migrant workers in Chennai district. The F-statistic is 1.118, 2.537, 1.024, 1.009, 0.10, 1.289 which is a measure of the variation between the groups relative to the variation within the groups of gender, age, marital status religion education and duration of stay in Chennai. This value indicates that there is some difference in dependency on social problems with the covid-19. The p-value (Sig.) associated with the F-statistic is 0.029, 0.011, 0.007, 0.316, 0.003, and 0.000 of gender, age, marital status religion education and duration of stay in Chennai respectively. Since the p-value is lesser than the typical significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected and H₁ is accepted based on the results of the ANOVA.

1.7 SUGGESTIONS

It is evident from the results obtained through the analysis that special attention and care should be made to manage future pandemics, particularly to address the migrant workers those who have come from the faraway distances. Community-level support system for the migrant workers by involving local self-government leaders, self-help group women leaders, and frontline health workers is also necessary. The government agencies may provide necessary basic requirement during the pandemic, so that this may help to maintain the morbidity distress caused by the pandemic.

1.8 CONCLUSIONS

In the field of migration studies, there has been very less number of research on the relationship between pandemics and migration before COVID-19. In general, there has been growing attention in the field to the key topic of health-related migration. When people living in this motherland work in different parts of the country to support their families financially through construction workers, hotel workers, miners, cleaners, agricultural workers, restaurant workers, retail, transport workers, social workers, maid and so on they face lot of problems out of them one is social aspects. This research made an attempt to bring the problems faced by the migrant worries during the pandemic situation. The p-value (Sig.) associated with the F-statistic is

0.029, 0.011, 0.007, 0.316, 0.003, and 0.000 of gender, age, marital status religion education and duration of stay in Chennai respectively. Since the p-value is lesser than the typical significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected and H₁ is accepted based on the results of the ANOVA. The statistical analysis is concluded that there is a constant relationship between the social aspects among the emigrant workers.

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